

Strategic Postoperative Management in High-Risk Cardiac Surgery: Navigating ECMO, Persistent Infection, and Pacemaker Dependency

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ABSTRACT

This case report describes the intensive management of a 46-year-old female with a history of left ventricular outflow tract (LVOT) obstruction who underwent redo sternotomy, aortic root enlargement, and mechanical valve replacement. Despite multiple interventions including ECMO, the patient's course was complicated by persistent bacteremia, challenges in weaning from mechanical ventilation, and multi-organ dysfunction. This case highlights the complexities of managing high-risk cardiac surgery patients in the ICU setting, emphasizing the need for multidisciplinary approaches and vigilant postoperative care.

Background: Patients with complex cardiac histories undergoing major surgeries like aortic valve replacement and LVOT obstruction management often face significant postoperative challenges. These include hemodynamic instability, infection risks, and the need for mechanical circulatory support, all of which necessitate a well-coordinated multidisciplinary approach.

Objective: To discuss the management complexities and multidisciplinary care approach in a high-risk cardiac surgery patient with multiple postoperative complications.

Keywords: Cardiac Surgery; Infection; ECMO

CASE REPORT

A 46-year-old female with a complex cardiac history including LVOT obstruction, presented with worsening symptoms of dyspnea, orthopnea, and fatigue, classified as NYHA Class III heart failure. Previous interventions included subaortic membrane resection four years prior to her current presentation. Due to progressive symptomatology and echocardiographic findings indicating severe LVOT obstruction and moderate to severe valvular regurgitations, she underwent a complex surgical procedure during this admission. The operation involved redo sternotomy, enlargement of the aortic root using a bovine pericardial patch (Nick's procedure), and replacement of the aortic valve with a 19 mm St Jude mechanical valve. Additionally, septal myomectomy was performed to address the subaortic membrane.

Immediate postoperative management was complicated by the need for VA ECMO due to unstable hemodynamics and severe respiratory failure. She required intensive vasopressor support to maintain adequate perfusion. She also experienced episodes of Torsades de Pointes and ventricular fibrillation, necessitating multiple defibrillations. Her cardiovascular management was challenging, complicated by pacemaker dependency due to complete heart block and persistent hypotension. Approximately one month after surgery, a permanent Micra AV pacemaker was implanted, stabilizing her heart rhythm and improving hemodynamics.

Throughout her ICU stay, our patient battled persistent bacteremia, initially suspected to be related to her mechanical valve, but without vegetative findings on repeated TEEs. The bacteremia was primarily due to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, complicated by the development of resistance to initial antibiotic regimens. Despite multiple antibiotic adjustments, including the use of ceftolozane-tazobactam, her infection persisted, necessitating prolonged courses of targeted therapy.

Her respiratory status was precarious, necessitating prolonged mechanical ventilation. Several attempts at weaning were unsuccessful, complicated by recurrent episodes of respiratory distress and fatigue. A tracheostomy was performed to facilitate weaning and long-term ventilation management.

Acute kidney injury (AKI) also developed, managed initially with continuous venovenous hemofiltration. Her renal function gradually improved, transitioning to less aggressive diuretic management. Metabolic imbalances including hypokalemia and hypernatremia were addressed through careful electrolyte management.

Gastrointestinal complications included episodes of gastrointestinal bleeding, managed conservatively with adjustments in proton pump inhibitor therapy and close monitoring. Nutritional support was challenging due to her critical state, managed via enteral feeding with close monitoring by the nutrition team.

After a prolonged stay of 51 days in the ICU, our patient's condition stabilized sufficiently to plan for discharge to a long-term acute care facility. Her discharge plan included detailed follow-up for her complex cardiac and infectious issues, ongoing anticoagulation management, and rehabilitation.

This case highlights the complexities of managing a high-risk cardiac surgery patient with multiple comorbidities and complications. The collaborative efforts of the multidisciplinary team were pivotal in navigating the myriad of challenges that presented during her extended hospitalization.

DISCUSSION

This case underscores the complexity of managing critically ill cardiac patients with extensive hospital exposures, particularly highlighting the challenge of persistent *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* bacteremia despite intensive antibiotic treatment. The difficulties in weaning from ECMO further emphasize the need for meticulous cardiovascular management and provide insights into effective strategies for similar future cases. This report contributes to the growing body of knowledge on the necessity of a tailored, multidisciplinary approach to achieve favorable outcomes.

The persistent bacteremia caused by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, known for its resistance mechanisms such as efflux pumps, enzyme production, and biofilm formation, exemplifies the challenges in treating infections resistant to conventional antibiotics. This situation necessitated the adoption of advanced pharmacologic strategies and highlighted the importance of real-time microbial surveillance and effective antibiotic stewardship.^[1] Stewardship in our case involved continuously adapting antibiotic strategies based on culture

results and sensitivity patterns, ensuring the use of the most effective therapies without promoting further resistance.^[2]

Moreover, managing these complex infections required a collaborative interdisciplinary approach. Close coordination among infectious disease specialists, pharmacists, microbiologists, and critical care physicians was crucial for interpreting data, predicting potential resistance pathways, and promptly adjusting treatment plans. This integrated team effort was essential for addressing complications swiftly, thereby enhancing the likelihood of a successful recovery.^[3]

Additionally, the management of our patient also illustrates the critical role and complexities of mechanical circulatory support in post-cardiac surgery care, particularly in the context of unstable hemodynamics that necessitated the use of VA ECMO. The use of ECMO provided vital support during a period of significant vulnerability, allowing for stabilization and recovery of cardiac function. However, this technology requires intricate balancing of anticoagulation, fluid management, and careful monitoring of systemic effects.^[4]

Additionally, the challenges associated with pacemaker dependency post-surgery call attention to the intersection of cardiac surgery and advanced cardiac device technology. Our patient's development of complete heart block, a serious and not uncommon complication post-heart surgery, necessitated the timely implantation of a pacemaker. This device not only stabilized her cardiac rhythm, but also significantly improved her prognosis by preventing potential fatal arrhythmias and enhancing cardiac output.

This aspect of care highlights the need for timely intervention and the necessity of keeping abreast with evolving technologies in cardiac pacing and their practical implications in clinical settings. For clinicians, understanding these technologies and their application can profoundly impact patient outcomes, emphasizing the need for ongoing education and training in the rapidly advancing field of cardiac care technology. The successful integration of such advanced therapeutic options requires not only technical expertise, but also a holistic approach to patient care, ensuring that all potential complications are anticipated and managed proactively.

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